

Freshwater Cooling Injection to Mitigate Saltwater Intrusion and Support Sustainable Groundwater Management

Ismail Abd-Elaty^{1*} Alban Kuriqi^{2,3} and Luis Garrote⁴

¹Department of Water and Water Structures Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Zagazig University, Zagazig 44519, Egypt, eng_abdelaty2006@yahoo.com,

²CERIS, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais 1, 1049-001, Lisbon, Portugal; alban.kuriqi@tecnico.ulisboa.pt; ORCID: 0000-0001-7464-8377

³Civil Engineering Department, University for Business and Technology, Pristina, Kosovo

⁴Department of Civil Engineering: Hydraulics, Energy and Environment, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain; l.garrote@upm.es

*Correspondence: alban.kuriqi@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Abstract

This study examined the influence of thermal forcing on saltwater intrusion into nearshore aquifers (SWI) in the context of sea level rise due to climate change and continued groundwater withdrawal due to increasing demand. The study used the SEAWAT code to test two case studies: the Henry problem as a benchmark and the Biscayne Aquifer, Florida, USA, as a real case. Simulations were performed for the base case, sea level rise (SLR), and inland groundwater recharge reductions. A new management method was proposed for mitigating SWI in nearshore aquifers using the Abstraction of saline water, Desalination, Cooling the desalinated water, and Injection into the aquifer (ADCI) strategy. The method was tested with different freshwater temperatures of 25, 20, 15, 10, and 5°C. The results showed that freshwater recharge in coastal regions is sensitive to the thermal regime, resulting in the attenuation of SWI. The results of this study are important for the sustainable management of groundwater resources in coastal areas to meet increasing water demands. The Biscayne salt repulsion reached +9.80 %, +10 %, +10.20 %, +10.30 %, and +10.50 % for changing the injection recharge by 25, 20, 15, 10, and 5°C. Future planning, design, and development of SWI mitigation measures should consider thermal regime effects. In addition, a cost–benefit analysis for this method using 3D models is needed to determine the feasibility and economic aspect of cooling water supply compared to current techniques.

Keywords: Aquifers; Desalination; Injection; SWI; Water abstraction

Notations

<i>ADCI:</i>	Abstracting Brackish water, Desalination, Cooling the Desalinated
<i>BA:</i>	Biscayne Aquifer
<i>FE:</i>	Finite Elements
<i>FD:</i>	Finite Difference
<i>HST3D:</i>	Heat and Solute Transport in Three-Dimensional groundwater flow systems
<i>IMT:</i>	Integrated MT3DMS Transport process
<i>MOCDENSE:</i>	A two-constituent solute transport model for groundwater having variable density
<i>MODFLOW:</i>	United States Geological Survey modular finite-difference flow model
<i>MT3DMS:</i>	Modular Transport Three-Dimensional Multispecies
<i>SWI:</i>	Saltwater Intrusion
<i>SEAWAT:</i>	Three-Dimensional Variable-Density Groundwater Flow
<i>SLR:</i>	Sea Level Rise
<i>SWT:</i>	Subsurface Water Technologies
<i>SUTRA:</i>	Model for Saturated-Unsaturated, Variable-Density Groundwater Flow with Solute or Energy Transport
<i>UAE:</i>	United Arab Emirate
<i>USA:</i>	United States of America
<i>VDF:</i>	Variable Density Flow Process
<i>AMSL:</i>	Above Mean Sea Level

1. Introduction

In recent decades, there have been several advances in detecting changes in groundwater levels and temperature [1, 2]. Thus, groundwater elevation and temperature changes lead to an integrated mechanism. Although many studies have argued that changes in permeability due to changes in aquifer viscosity can lead to changes in groundwater levels, continuous observations and measurements of these changes are limited to few reported cases [1, 3], and the documented relationships between aquifer column changes and parameters show few responses to dynamic effects [4]. Mathematical or numerical models are used to infer changes in permeability based on previous studies of [Langevin, et al. \[5\]](#) and [Kohout \[6\]](#) or from samples of water quality, water table [7], and temperature [8]. [Lee and Cheng \[9\]](#) achieved groundwater level changes of up to 0.716 m. Temperature changes of up to nearly 0.071 °C were observed in Mile Well, Yunnan Province, China, in response to

earthquakes with a seismic energy density greater than $1.097 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Jkg.m}^{-3}$ from 2004 to 2012. Based on the aquifer parameters analyzed from the tidal response, the amplitudes of the inferred changes in transmissivity and storage coefficient correlate well with the changes in the water table and temperature. The magnitude of the change in transmissivity was much greater than that of the storage coefficient.

The influence of temperature might have a key role in simulating groundwater flow and saltwater intrusion. The density and viscosity of fluids are affected by temperature and change as a function of temperature distribution. Henry [10] developed numerical and laboratory tests considering temperature and salinity. Henry [10] original semi-analytical solution neglected temperature dispersion. Groundwater salinization involves three processes: hydrostatic fluid pressure, solute transport mechanism, and energy transfer due to temperature changes, including conduction, convection, and latent heat transfer in groundwater and solid aquifer matrix [1, 7].

SWI should be sustainably managed to protect fresh groundwater resources from depletion. To take measures to control SWI, an in-depth study based on theoretical, numerical, or practical analysis is required [7, 11, 12]. There are various measures to control seawater intrusion and protect groundwater resources. The main principle of protection is to increase the volume of fresh groundwater and reduce the volume of saline water. Todd [13] presented several ways to mitigate SWI, including reducing pumping rates and relocating wells, installing physical subsurface barriers, natural and artificial recharge, wastewater reinjection, brackish water withdrawal, combining injection and withdrawal systems, and constructing a trough (i.e., interceptor channel) parallel to the shoreline. All these methods have their advantages and limitations and are site-specific.

Pu, et al. [14] conducted experimental and numerical studies to investigate the impact of cold and hot freshwater recharge on coastal aquifers; the results showed that the SWI was fitting using cold freshwater recharge compared with hot water. Increasing the freshwater and/or saline water temperatures has increased the SWI compared with isothermal conditions. Blanco-Coronas, et al. [15] studied temperature distribution in coastal aquifers. The groundwater modeling and field investigation results showed that applying heat tracers in hydrogeological studies is growing in interest, reliable and low cost. Also, the study pointed out the major processes and parameters that influence temperature application in coastal aquifers. Cogswell and Heiss [16] studied the impact of controlling the climate and seasonal

temperature on the biogeochemical transformations in unconfined coastal aquifers; the results indicated that the efficiency of nitrate removal increased from 5% to 88% by increasing the freshwater temperature from 5°C to 35°C.

2. Hydraulic technique and saltwater intrusion

Using hydraulic barriers for SWI mitigation in coastal aquifers, including the three techniques for recharge, abstraction, and combination of two methods, has more attention and popularity than other control methods. The available water resource for the hydraulic including the abstraction and desalination of seawater or brackish water using small-scale reverse osmosis (RO) plants to support the urban water supply, the treated wastewater from these communities is used for recharge to the coastal aquifers as an economic step in this system. The positive technique for the hydraulic barriers is the recharge method is high popularity and widely suggested to use in SWI management [17, 18]. Worldwide attention on seawater desalination is drawing due to the growth of annual water demand.

Sun and Semprich [19] examined air and freshwater injection to control SWI in coastal aquifers; the results showed that applying the freshwater injection is better than using air. Zuurbier, et al. [20] applied three subsurface water technologies (SWT) to manage freshwater in a coastal aquifer; the results showed that SWT is better and more economical for different hydrogeological problems such as SWI and upcoming. Abd-Elaty, et al. [21] applied brackish water abstraction, treated wastewater recharge, and a combination of two techniques in the Gaza aquifer, Palestine; the results showed that the application of the two methods is highly effective for SWI mitigation in high-stress water shortage compared with recharge of treated wastewater and desalination of brackish water respectively. Sowe, et al. [22] applied an optimization pumping strategy of brackish water to control SWI in Wadi Ham, UAE. The simulation results showed that the intrusion was fitting using 16 pumpings well with a total pumping rate of 8000 m³ d⁻¹ at 1500 m from the shoreline. Abd-Elaty and Zelenakova [23] investigated the ability of shallow and deep aquifers on SWI management in the Nile Delta aquifer; the study indicated that the TRAD method is better for reducing the intrusion for in shallow and deep aquifers compared with the other methods as physical barriers.

This technique's limitation includes the high construction and operation costs with burdens energy for the positive deep recharge wells. However, the better solution is to achieve pond recharge in unconfined aquifers [17, 18].

Therefore, the main objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of a novel method called Abstraction of saline water, Desalination, Cooling the desalinated water, and Injection into the aquifer (ADCI), considering different freshwater temperatures of 25, 20, 15, 10, and 5° C. The rest of the paper is organized for the analysis of the current study for the two methods in a hypothetical benchmark and a real case study as follows: [Section 2](#) presents the data set used in the analysis, numerical modeling, and the new proposed approach to reduce SWI; [Section 3](#) presents the main findings; [Section 4](#) discusses the relevance and applicability of the ADCI method; finally, the main conclusions drawn from this study were presented in [Section 5](#).

3. Materials and Methods

This study consists of a numerical analysis using SEAWAT code and applied for two case studies, Henry's hypothetical problem and a field study area of Biscayne aquifer, Florida, USA, to investigate the efficiency of ADCI on SWI management. Figure 1 presents a flow chart of the investigation methodology adopted in this study.

Fig. 1. Schematic presentation of methodology.

3.1 Cases study

3.1.1 Henry hypothetical problem test

Figure 2 presents a definition sketch of an SWI test model using Henry's problem as a hypothetical test study. The domain is 2 m horizontal, 1 m vertical, and 0.10 m wide (Fig. A1).

Fig. 2. Henry's problem boundary condition for vertical and incline aquifer bed slope.

The finite-difference model grid consists of 4 rows with 80 columns and 40 layers. The cell dimensions are 0.025 m x 0.025 m, except for the cells in the last column, which are 0.0025 m x 0.025 m in size for the x and y direction, respectively, and the cells in the narrow column to locate more precisely the hydrostatic of the saline water at 2 m. The injection well was assigned using inflow rates of $0.5702 \text{ m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ to each cell of column 1 (Table 1).

Table 1. The values of hydraulic parameters used in the numerical model simulation.

Parameter	Henry's problem	Biscayne aquifer	Units
Saltwater head (h_s)	1	0.22	m
Inland Freshwater Flux (q_{in})	5.702	15	$\text{m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$
Saltwater density (ρ_s)	1025	1025	kg m^{-3}
Freshwater density (ρ_f)	1000	1000	kg m^{-3}
Specific Storage	0	1.967×10^{-6}	m^{-1}
Longitudinal dispersivity (α_L)	0	10	m

Transverse dispersivity (α_T)	0	1	m
Molecular diffusion coefficient (D^*)	0.57024	0	$\text{m}^2 \text{day}^{-1}$
Solid (porous media) density (ρ_s)	2.80	2.70	kg m^{-3}
Bulk density (ρ_b)	1.82	2.16	kg m^{-3}
Solid (porous media) heat capacity ($C_{P_{solid}}$)	920	840	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
Fluid (water) heat capacity ($C_{P_{fluid}}$)	4183	4183	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
Solid (porous media) thermal conductivity ($k_{T_{solid}}$)	2.90	2.15	$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
Fluid (water) thermal conductivity ($k_{T_{fluid}}$)	0.61	0.61	$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
Bulk thermal diffusivity (Dm_{temp})	0.12	0.19	$\text{m}^2 \text{day}^{-1}$
Distribution coefficient for temperature (Kd_{temp})	0.00022	0.0002	$\text{m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$
Saltwater concentration (C_s)	35700	35.70	kg m^{-3}
Hydraulic conductivity (k) (Isotropic)	864	1000	m day^{-1}
Porosity (n)	0.35	0.20	Dimension less
Reference kinematic viscosity (ν_o)	0.0864	0.0864	$\text{m}^2 \text{day}^{-1}$
Reference dynamic viscosity (μ_o)	86.4	86.4	$\text{Kg m}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$
Reference concentration (C_o)	0	0	kg m^{-3}
Reference temperature (T_o)	25°	25°	c
Density changes with concentration	0.715	0.715	Dimension less
Density changes with temperature	-0.375	-0.375	Dimension less
Total variation-diminishing solver	TVD	TVD	-
Number of columns	80	43	-
Number of rows	40	34	-
Initial time step	0.01	0.01	day

At sea, the specified head of the aquifer system was developed using a constant saltwater head assigned using a 1 m and a concentration of 35 kg m^{-3} [1]. In addition, the temperature effect was applied by assigning the right ocean boundary conditions and the left aquifer boundary by a constant temperature of 25 degrees, as shown in [Figure 2](#).

3.1.2 Biscayne Aquifer study area

The Biscayne Aquifer (BA) locates is a real-world coastal zone near Deering Estate, Florida, USA, in the Cutler Ridge area between latitudes $25^\circ 36''$ and $25^\circ 38''$ North and longitudes $80^\circ 17''$ and $80^\circ 20''$ West ([Fig. 3a](#)). This aquifer covers an area of about 4,000 sq.

mi. It provides freshwater supply for more than 4 million people in southeastern Florida with a daily yield of 700 million gpd [24].

Fig. 3. Study area for (a) main karst aquifers in Florida (USA) [25], (b) study case location for Biscayne Bay, Florida [5], and c) characterization of geologic and hydrogeologic properties of the surficial aquifer system across central Miami-Dade County, North of the Snapper Creek Well Field study area: adapted from Cunningham, et al. [8].

The climate of this region is hot and humid rainy summers and mild winters, where the annual precipitation is 1507 mm, and the annual evapotranspiration is between 1220 mm to 1320 mm [26]. The aquifer receives recharge to maintain the groundwater table above mean sea level (a.msl). The recharge sources include rainfall which is subjected to evapotranspiration and surface runoff. The aquifer abstraction serves the water supply for the drinking and irrigation water for agriculture in Miami-Dade County [27]. In dry seasons, groundwater levels in South Florida range from 0.60 m to 1.2 m below the ground surface. The groundwater is usually standing water over the Holocene deposits during the wet seasons [28].

The aquifer is coastal, shallow, unconfined, and heterogeneous with high water levels and formed by less-permeable sand and sandstone to highly permeable karstic limestone [27]. Also, it is a shallow layer of highly porous. Also, it is an unconfined aquifer, and the hydro-stratigraphy is presented in Figure 3c [27]. The lithology of the aquifer is dominated by sand layers at the surface and carbonates and minor sandstone deep layers. These fractured and often karstic rocks facilitate the formation of far-reaching regional groundwater systems between recharge and discharge areas regional groundwater flow systems even at moderate elevation differences of less than 100 m [29].

The simulation model was applied to a real case study to identify the influence of coupled temperature and concentration variations on SWI. This aquifer was analyzed by Kohout [6], who indicated that seawater is circulated through the aquifer. About 12.5% of the groundwater was discharged to Biscayne Bay using field study and monitoring wells (Fig. 4b) in southeast Florida. Lee and Cheng [9] developed a 2-D FE, a vertical cross-sectional model using a steady-state condition to study SWI encroachment to the BA in Coulter, Florida, USA.

3.2 Coupled solute and heat transport model

The variable density of combined groundwater flow and solute transport problems could be solved by finite elements (FE) of SUTRA [30], analytical elements by Strack [31], and finite difference (FD) using SEAWAT [5, 11, 32], MOCDENSE [33], and HST3D [34]. The current study was developed and solved by the SEAWAT_V4 code [4], which is a combination of MODFLOW [35] and MT3DMS [36, 37]. This version was developed to solve the solute and heat transport, where the fluid density and viscosity are calculated as a function of one or

more species. The variable density flow (VDF) process solves the variable density flow equation in terms of the freshwater head [11], Eq.1:

$$\nabla \left[\rho \frac{\mu_o}{\mu} K_o \left(\nabla h_o + \frac{\rho - \rho_o}{\rho_o} \nabla z \right) \right] = \rho S_{s,0} \left(\frac{\partial h_o}{\partial t} \right) + \theta \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial C} \right) \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \right) - \rho_s q_s \quad (1)$$

The Integrated MT3DMS Transport (IMT) process solves the solute transport equation, Eqs. 2 and 3:

$$\left(1 + \frac{\rho_b K_d^k}{\theta} \right) \left(\frac{\partial (\theta C^k)}{\partial t} \right) = \nabla \left[\theta \left(D_m^k + \alpha \frac{q}{\theta} \right) \cdot \nabla C^k \right] - \nabla \cdot (q C^k) - q_s^k * C_s^k \quad (2)$$

The governing equation of the heat transport equation [4] express as:

$$\left(1 + \frac{1-\theta}{\theta} * \frac{\rho}{\rho_s} \frac{C_{psolid}}{C_{pfluid}} \right) \left(\frac{\partial (\theta T)}{\partial t} \right) = \nabla \left[\theta \left(\frac{K_{Tbulk}}{\theta \rho C_{pfluid}} + \alpha \frac{q}{\theta} \right) \cdot \nabla T \right] - \nabla \cdot (q T) - q_s^k * T_s \quad (3)$$

Dynamic viscosity in SEAWAT is developed as a function of only temperature and solute concentration; the general equation is the following term [4] expressed as Eq. 4:

$$\mu = \mu_o + \sum_{k=1}^{NS} \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial C^k} (C^k - C_o^k) + \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial T} (T - T_o) \quad (4)$$

Where, ρ_o : fluid density [ML⁻³] at the reference concentration and temperature; μ : dynamic viscosity [ML⁻¹ T⁻¹]; K_o : hydraulic conductivity [LT⁻¹]; h_o : hydraulic head [L], ρ_b : bulk density [ML⁻³], ρ_s : density of the solid [ML⁻³], $S_{s,0}$: specific storage [L⁻¹], t : time [T]; θ : porosity [-]; C : salt concentration [ML⁻³], q : specific discharge [LT⁻¹], q_s^k : a source or sink [T⁻¹], D_m^k : is the molecular diffusion coefficient [L²T⁻¹] for species k ; α : is the dispersivity tensor [L]; K_d^k : distribution coefficient of species k [L³ M⁻¹], C^k : the concentration of species k [ML⁻³], C_s^k : the source or sink concentration [ML⁻³], C_{psolid} : specific heat capacity of the solid [L² T⁻² °K⁻¹], C_{pfluid} : specific heat capacity of the fluid [L² T⁻² °K⁻¹], K_{Tbulk} : bulk thermal conductivity of the aquifer material [ML³ T⁻² °K⁻¹], and T_s : source temperature [°K]. μ_o : reference dynamic viscosity [ML⁻¹ T⁻¹]; μ_o : reference dynamic viscosity [ML⁻¹ T⁻¹]; C_o^k : the concentration of species k [ML⁻³]; T : temperature [°K]; T_o : reference temperature [°K].

3.3 Modeling of Henry's problem

The numerical results for Henry's problem using the SEAWAT model were compared with some known solutions. Figure 4a shows the results of the 0.5 Isochlor position obtained

by SEAWAT. The numerical solution SEAWAT shows a good match compared with the different solutions, where the 0.5 Isochlor positions reached 0.855 m from the seaside.

Fig. 4. The 0.5 Isochlor counters in Henry problem at the base case for a) without temperature and b) isothermal case.

In contrast, the total salt mass in the model domain reached 0.45 kg. The results were compared with the other codes of Henry [10], such as the HST3D and SUTRA codes and the semi-analytical solution [38]. A good agreement was found between the current model results and the published materials [2]. The isothermal model was simulated for the constant temperature of 25°C. The results showed that the intrusion of 0.5 Isochlor reached 1.035 m from the base of the seaside and 0.66 kg for salt mass. This means the temperature significantly affects SWI in coastal aquifers, as shown in Figure 4b.

3.4 Modeling of Biscayne Aquifer's

The BA domains, geometry, hydrological and hydraulic parameters were deduced from the available literature. The Biscayne aquifer has a rectangular domain of 2165 m in length and an average depth of 33 m, which was considered, as shown in Figure 3b. Detailed geologic and hydraulic aspects of the aquifer at Deering Estate were published by Langevin, et al. [5]. The model grids are 43 columns, 34 layers, and 1 row, with 50 x 1 x 1 m cell dimensions in the x, z, and y directions, respectively (Fig. A2).

The Biscayne aquifer is one of the world's most productive karst aquifers, with measured transmissivities of 46634 to 186538 m²day⁻¹ [39, 40]. Rogers, et al. [41] estimated hydraulic conductivity to increase by four orders of magnitude to approximately 86400 mday⁻¹ as the distance from shore increases. Jacob's solution is also effective for aquifer

parameter estimation in Miami Beach. The aquifer porosity has been estimated by [Renken, et al. \[40\]](#), with a range from 10 to over 50%, while [Cunningham, et al. \[8\]](#) estimated the value to range from less than 6 to greater than 50% using core samples and digital optical borehole wall images. [Motz and Brown \[42\]](#) estimated the horizontal hydraulic conductivity range from 10368 mday⁻¹ to 26784 mday⁻¹. [Yeboah-Forson and Whitman \[43\]](#) Estimated hydraulic conductivities are much larger than the range of maximum values of 8640 mday⁻¹ to 26784 mday⁻¹ reported for aquifer tests conducted in the Biscayne aquifer.

According to the literature, the porosity of the aquifer is 0.20. Horizontal and vertical hydraulic conductivities were 1000 and 100 mday⁻¹, respectively. The longitudinal and transverse dispersivities α_L and α_T were 10 and 1 m, respectively. Also, the recharge is 380 mm (i.e., annual recharge from rainfall). These parameters were measured with groundwater pumping tests [4]. The thermal parameters were estimated for Henry's problem and the Biscayne aquifer. The values are presented in Table 1 and based on [4]. The solid density of the porous media is calculated according to Eqs. 5-7:

$$\rho_b = \rho_s(1 - \theta) \quad (5)$$

Also, the thermal distribution factor is estimated using the following formula

$$K_d = \frac{C_{p\ solid}}{\rho_{fluid} C_{p\ fluid}} \quad (6)$$

The bulk thermal conductivity is calculated using

$$K_{T\ bulk} = \theta K_{T\ fluid} + (1 - \theta)K_{T\ solid} \quad (7)$$

The thermal molecular diffusion coefficient is calculated using Eq. 8:

$$D_{m,temperature} = \frac{K_{Tbulk}}{\theta \rho_{fluid} C_{p\ fluid}} \quad (8)$$

Where, ρ_b : bulk density [ML⁻³]; ρ_s : solid density [ML⁻³]; ρ_{fluid} : fluid density [ML⁻³]; θ : porosity [-]; $C_{p\ solid}$: specific heat capacity of the solid [L² T⁻² °K⁻¹]; $C_{p\ fluid}$: specific heat capacity of the fluid [L² T⁻² °K⁻¹]; $K_{T\ bulk}$: bulk thermal conductivity of the aquifer material [ML³ T⁻² °K⁻¹]; K_d : thermal distribution factor [-]; and D_m : thermal molecular diffusion coefficient [L² T⁻¹].

The densities of fresh groundwater ρ_f and saline water ρ_s were 1000 and 1025 kgm⁻³, respectively. The groundwater flux considered a specified flux boundary into the inland boundary of the model domain condition on the land side ($x = -1550$ m), with the freshwater flux being 15 m³day⁻¹m⁻¹ of the shoreline. The concentration was equal to the freshwater

concentration on the side of 1 kg m^{-3} . On the other hand, at the sea boundary where $0 \leq x \leq 615 \text{ m}$, a specified head (seawater level) boundary condition (water level) was considered on the head by 0.22 m (AMSL). The concentration was equal to the seawater concentration of 35 kg m^{-3} .

The study simulation was conducted using SEAWAT 4 under steady and isothermal conditions. Figure 5a shows the concentration results only where the intrusion reached 478 m from the shoreline for 0.5 Isochlor with a salt mass of 163400 kg .

Fig. 5. The 0.5 Isochlor counters in Biscayne aquifer at the base case for a) concentration only and b) isothermal case.

The current simulation results were compared with those of Langevin, et al. [5] in the same study case, with a good qualitative agreement between the results of the two models. Furthermore, the Biscayne isothermal model using the constant temperature of 25°C , shown in Figures 5b, in which the intrusion reached 504 m for 0.5 Isochlor with a salt mass of 190132 kg . The isothermal conditions have influenced the salinity of the aquifer and increased the SWI.

3.5 Modeling scenarios

The model was run to simulate the future expected in SLR with a reduction in fresh groundwater recharge. Also, fresh groundwater management was simulated to examine the influence of the ADCI approach on SWI mitigation in coastal regions. The considered scenarios of recharge water temperature were 25 °, 20 °, 15 °, 10 °, and 5° C for the Henry problem and Biscayne aquifer cases.

4. Results

4.1 Impact of SLR and reduction in freshwater recharge on SWI

The Henry hypothetical problem test model was simulated by changing the saltwater heads to 1.10 m due to the expected influence of sea level rise (SLR). Fresh groundwater was decreased by 20% from landside recharge ($0.5702 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$) to $0.45616 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$. The intrusion of 0.5 Isochlor increases to 1.395 m for the isothermal case compared to the baseline case of 1.035 m with an increase to 0.98073 kg with a comparison of 0.65658 kg in the baseline case. The groundwater salt repulsion (%), Eq. 9:

$$\text{Salt repulsion} = (C_0 - C) / C_0 \% \quad (9)$$

C_0 is the initial groundwater salt concentration, and C is the concentration in the proposed scenario. A negative repulsion value means that the groundwater salinity increased. In contrast, a positive repulsion value means that the groundwater salinity decrease. The calculated total aquifer salt repulsion reached -49.37%, as shown in [Figure 6a](#).

Fig. 6. The 0.5 Isochlor counters for combined SLR with a reduction in fresh groundwater recharge for a) the Henry test case and b) the Biscayne aquifer.

Also, the expected SLR in Southeast Florida changed the Biscayne aquifer boundary conditions, reaching 0.3556 m in the estimate for 2050 by the sea level rise working group [24, 44]. Also, the reduction in fresh groundwater recharge by 30% is $10.50 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$. The simulation results showed that the intrusion of 0.5 Isochlor increased to 679 m (i.e., compared with 504 m at the baseline case) with 205671 kg for salt mass (compared with 190132 kg at the baseline case) with increasing salt repulsion reaching -8.17% (Fig. 6b).

4.2 Management of SWI using the ADCI method

The ADCI method was applied to two cases of saline water management in coastal aquifers. Henry's problem was simulated using the ADCI method. The abstraction well by the brackish water is applied by 60% from landside recharge rates ($0.5702 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$) to reach $0.34212 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$ at 0.30 m from the seaside with 0.80 m depth. The abstracted water was desalinated using a suitable method, and the water was supplied to the community. The wastewater was treated, and the cooling was set at 25°C . The cooling water was recharged using well recharge rates of 30% of the total landside recharge ($0.5702 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$) to reach 0.17106

$\text{m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$ (Fig. 7); the well distance from the seaside is 1.50 m with 0.40 m in depth at a constant temperature of 25°C .

Fig. 7. Relationship between the intrusion and proposed scenarios for the Henry test and Biscayne aquifer.

The same process of the ADCI method was applied to the Biscayne aquifer, and it was simulated at a constant temperature of 25°C ; the brackish water was abstracted using well abstraction rates were 60% from the base case ($15 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$) to reach $9 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$ with a depth of 30 m from the top surface and distance of 150 m from the shoreline. The Desalination, wastewater treatment, and treated water cooling were done. The recharge well for the cooling water was applied 30% from the base case ($15 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$) to reach $4.50 \text{ m}^3\text{day}^{-1}$ at 14.20 m and 300 m (Fig. 7a).

The SWI of the Henry test case decreased and reached 1.055 m, while the salt mass decreased and reached 0.71 kg with a repulsion of +28.60%. Moreover, the SWI of the Biscayne aquifer reached 518 m with a salt mass of 185380 kg and a salt repulsion of +9.80%. It can be concluded that SWI could be decreased using the ADCI method in coastal regions (Fig. 7b).

4.3 Impact of different recharge cooling temperatures on SWI

This scenario was developed to predict the freshwater-seawater interface's position considering the temperature's influence. The combined model of rising sea levels and reducing aquifer recharge (i.e., compared with 25⁰) was simulated for these scenarios by recharging the freshwater at a constant temperature of 20°C, 15°C, 10°C, and 5°C. The thermal parameters of the aquifer are presented in Table 1. The results of this scenario for the Henry test case indicate that the intrusion length, measured by the 0.5 Isochlor, reached 1.04 m, 1.025 m, 1.005 m, and 0.99 m (Fig.8a), with a salt mass of 0.69 kg, 0.6802 kg, 0.67 kg, and 0.66kg, respectively (Fig. 8b).

Fig. 8. Relationship between the Henry test salinity and temperatures effect for a) intrusion length and b) salt mass.

The salt repulsion reached +28.60 %, +29.60 %, +30.70 %, +31.90 %, and +33.20 %. The distribution of salinity and temperature for Henry's problem at different temperatures are presented in Figure A3. These results show that the SWI is decreased with more injection of cooling freshwater recharge; moreover, the % of salt repulsion is increased using the ADCI method. Figure 9a represents the results of 0.5 Isochlor counters in the Biscayne aquifer to reach 511 m, 506 m, 498 m, and 490 m.

Fig. 9. Relationship between the Biscayne aquifer salinity and temperatures effect for a) intrusion length and b) salt mass.

The aquifer salt mass was estimated to reach 185156 kg, 184857 kg, 184587 kg, and 184229 kg, respectively (Fig. 9b). Spatial results are presented in Figure A4. The Biscayne salt repulsion reached +9.80 %, +10 %, +10.20 %, +10.30 %, and +10.50 %. These scenarios showed that recharging freshwater with low temperatures could improve the aquifer salinity and decrease the saline water intrusion in coastal regions. The results of the Biscayne Aquifer showed the same trends for the test case using the Henry case. Figure A4 presents the distribution of different temperatures with the salinity and temperatures. This study provides practical insights for sustainable and effective management of the SWI in high water stresses as it consists of water reuse.

4.4 Feasibility of the ADCI method

The TRAD method's cost was estimated by Whitelaw, et al. [45] and Misra [46], which included the initial costs of the artificial recharge by 0.551 \$m⁻³ and 0.001 \$m⁻³ for well and pond recharge. Also, the running cost was 0.021 \$ m⁻³year⁻¹ and 0.001 \$m⁻³year⁻¹, with the high economic feasibility for recharge ponds (Table 2). This system will add to the cost of cooling.

Table 2. The cost values for different processes related to the ADCI method.

Case	Parameter	Cost (\$)	Units
Construction cost	Fixed Drilling well cost (C_{DW})	1000	$\$ m^{-1}$
	Abstraction cost (C_A)	0.42	$\$ m^3$
	Desalination cost (C_D)	0.60	$\$ m^3$
Water price cost	Treatment cost (C_T)	0.60	$\$ m^3$
	Cooling cost (C_C)	1.2	$\$ m^3$
	Recharge cost (R_C)	0.48	$\$ m^3$

To reduce this system cost, the study recommends applying the agriculture schedule in low air temperatures and by night when the irrigation water temperature is reduced compared with the daily air temperature. The system costs include the well drilling cost of \$ 100 per meter, abstraction cost of $0.42 \$m^{-3}$, desalination, and treatment cost of $\$m^{-3}$, cooling cost of $1.2 \$m^{-3}$, and recharge cost of $0.48 \$m^{-3}$. The cost description and values are published by [Qahman and Larabi \[47\]](#).

5. Discussion

[Byrne, et al. \[48\]](#) and [Ramasamy and Surendran \[49\]](#) warn of the potential impacts of climate change on freshwater temperature increases in coastal regions, which has implications for sustainable groundwater resource management and future coastal planning. This study presents a new method for mitigating SWI called ADCI. The ADCI method is an effective method that can be applied in coastal regions with nearshore aquifers to accelerate the influence on SWI abstraction through three functions: saltwater withdrawal, freshwater recharge, and the thermal effect of desalination. In addition, the results of the desalination study will be considered in future aquifer planning, management, and injection (ADCI) as a new methodology for managing water resources in coastal regions, which will help decision-makers make better decisions.

The analysis was conducted for the base case for concentration and isothermal conditions for the Henry problem cases and the Biscayne aquifer [\[41\]](#). In addition, the model was applied to study the effects of SLR and fresh groundwater reduction on groundwater

recharge. The results showed that the future effects of climate change on saline hydrostatic pressure and groundwater recharge increased the salinity of the aquifer. The results agree with those published by [Abd-Elaty, et al. \[2\]](#). The temperature of the aquifer and ocean affects the flux and distribution of salinity [\[15\]](#). The temperature scenarios for the recharge water were set as 25, 20, 15, 10, and 5 °C, respectively. These scenarios showed that the salinity of the aquifer was reduced, and the fresh groundwater was increased. The results agree with [Pu, et al. \[12\]](#), who indicated that saline water intrusion decreases by decreasing the temperature of fresh water.

[Nguyen, et al. \[50\]](#) showed that the high temperature of salt water at the ocean or sea boundaries increases hydraulic conductivity, decreases seawater density and hydrostatic force, increases mass transfer between aquifer and ocean, and increases submarine groundwater discharge. Although this method is positive for controlling SWI, it reduces the storage of fresh groundwater and the gradient between the saline water and freshwater and reaches the base case limit. [Pu, et al. \[14\]](#) have shown that hot freshwater recharge significantly exceeds SWI, while cold freshwater recharge reduces salinity distribution. However, these results could mitigate SWI by replenishing low freshwater temperatures in aquifers through irrigation at night when daytime air temperatures are high. In addition, a cost-effective and sustainable analysis of energy and resource use is needed to consider the feasibility and economic costs of applying the ADCI method in more detail.

A major limitation of this study is using a vertical cross-section area to simulate the effects of injection and withdrawal of water in wells. Future studies will need a 3D model to guide radial flow behavior. However, the feasibility and economic aspects, sustainability, energy consumption, and resource consumption of the ADCI method for practical applications must be carefully evaluated.

The proposed ADCI method is an effective method that can be applied in coastal aquifers to accelerate the control of SWI through three functions: saline water withdrawal, freshwater recharge, and thermal effect. In addition, the results of this study provide solution-oriented insights for future planning, management, and design of water resource management in coastal regions.

The practical application of this system in the irrigation process is by recharging the irrigation water at low air temperatures in the morning or at night where the water is low temperatures; this can reduce the SWI by recharge process. This system will support the

freshwater supplies and the specified head aquifer system by sustaining groundwater heads. It will achieve sustainable groundwater resource management in coastal zones worldwide.

However, a detailed feasibility analysis of the water cooling cost using ADCI must be considered for the application to large hydrogeological systems using 3D modeling.

6. Conclusions

Saltwater intrusion in coastal regions threatens groundwater resource availability and reduces fresh groundwater storage. This study aimed to investigate the effects of fresh groundwater recharge on groundwater salinity in the Henry and Biscayne Aquifer, Florida, USA. The study analyzes three cases; the first is the base case, the second is the combination of increasing the saline water level by the expected SLR and decreasing the groundwater recharge, and the third is the management using freshwater cooling, where the saline water is extracted, desalinated, cooled, and freshwater is injected into the aquifer (ADCI), with different temperature levels of 25, 20, 15, 10, and 5°C, respectively. The results show that the salinity of the aquifer improves, and the SWI decreases by injecting cooling water. The results of 0.5 Isochlor counters in the Biscayne aquifer reach 511 m, 506 m, 498 m, and 490 m according to the considered temperature values.

The study recommends that irrigation can be done at night when freshwater temperatures are low. The impact of climate change by increasing irrigation water temperatures can be considered in future development to increase freshwater storage in coastal areas. For management plans, conducting a cost-benefit analysis, sustainable energy use, and resource use is recommended to examine the cost of gain from using the ADCI method.

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Appendixes

Fig. A1. Biscayne Aquifer, Florida Boundary conditions for (a) heads and (b) Concentration

Fig. A2. Biscayne aquifer, Florida Boundary conditions of (a) heads and (b) Concentration.

Fig. A3. Salinity distribution (figures on left) and temperature (figures on right) for Henry's problem at different temperatures.

Fig. A4. Salinity distribution (figures on left) and temperature (figures on right) for Biscayne Aquifer at different temperatures.

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